

Earth Science in Action for Tomorrow's World

Earth Observation Science Strategy

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FOREWORD

At this pivotal moment in time, humanity finds itself at a crossroads. Climate change, environment biodiversity loss, pollution and extreme events impact all inhabitants of our planet, some to a disproportionately greater degree, resulting in profound societal challenges. As a space agency it is our responsibility to apply the Earth observing tools at our disposal to inform and decide along which road to travel. The choice will ultimately determine the route to a more sustainable future, and aid transformation towards a more resilient society.

ESA's new Earth Observation Science Strategy provides a basis for implementation choices built on a solid scientific foundation. Today, Earth is more closely scrutinised and monitored by satellites than at any other time in our history. ESA has taken a leadership role by pioneering Earth Explorer research satellites with new observing capabilities, conceiving, developing, and implementing the Copernicus Sentinel series of satellites in cooperation with the European Union, and by developing European weather satellites in collaboration with EUMETSAT. The

ESA-developed Earth observing infrastructure, together with European national and international partner missions, and a rapidly growing commercial fleet, enables more timely, detailed, frequent, and widespread provision of information than ever before that span the needs of public, governmental and private users, supporting scientific enquiry, important public policy objectives and commercial endeavours.

At a time when the ESA Strategy 2040¹ seeks to further stimulate and strengthen these developments and lift Europe's space ambitions, the Earth Observation Science Strategy is fully aligned with the objective of protecting our planet. It embraces Earth observation-based scientific activities that lead the world in the sustainable and responsible use of space to help bring about a better, greener and safer future.

Simonetta Cheli

Director of ESA Earth Observation Programmes

¹ *ESA Strategy 2040 - ESA's vision for the European space sector by 2040*

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A science-driven approach lies at the heart of the ESA's Earth Observation Programmes, and the new Science Strategy provides the basis to increase the collective understanding of our evolving planet and the development of actionable information in tackling serious global environmental issues and the resulting challenges. The new Earth Observation (EO) Science Strategy outlines a vision for ESA Earth science through 2040 which is consistent and coherent with the ESA-wide Strategy 2040. It presents priorities and accompanying approaches that both reflect the need for discovery science, as well as the ability to respond to specific scientific and societal challenges. It identifies the areas of science that ESA needs to respond to, along the full value chain: from the development of innovative EO missions through to excellent Earth science and uptake of new observations by the user and applications community.

At the heart of the EO Science Strategy are overarching science themes and guiding questions that encapsulate pressing Earth system science issues and critical knowledge gaps in which EO satellite technology provides a unique contribution, either leveraging existing or near-future data sources, or by developing new capabilities and filling observation gaps.

The EO Science Strategy identifies four key strategic areas of action:

- **frontier science and discovery**
- **from science to societal benefits**
- **reducing critical knowledge gaps**
- **filling critical observation gaps**

The first area has the objective to pursue excellent, innovative, inspirational and impactful frontier science as a primary driver of innovation in EO Programme activities. The second area has the objective to develop the scientific knowledge and capacity by which to deliver high-quality validated, trusted, and actionable information products relevant for developing green solutions and the response to national, international and global policy frameworks. The third area is to ensure that the EO science community takes full advantage of the opportunities offered by the heritage, existing and new missions that will be launched in the next several years to advance our understanding of the Earth system and maximise scientific return. The fourth area is to develop and implement an architectural blueprint for an EO system-of-systems to guide long-term ESA research and technology preparation, mission implementation and operation of a coherent and sustainable space-based EO ecosystem by which to fill critical observation gaps.

The EO Science Strategy recognises that different timeframes are associated with EO Programme implementation in response to each of the four strategic areas of action. Use of data from ongoing and new missions using novel methods or innovative approaches provide the means to address overarching science themes and guiding questions on a shorter timescale e.g., within one or two consecutive three-year segments. Similarly, smaller and more expeditious missions can also be implemented within a short timeframe to deliver new observations and timely scientific progress. By contrast, the development lifecycle of ambitious flagship research missions, which provide new types of fundamental and novel observations are longer term. They require technology development and scientific maturation, resulting in a longer development and yielding scientific breakthrough results after 10–15 years. The strategy, therefore, also provides the basis to guide the technology development required for the implementation of more complex future missions to be realised over this timeframe.

The strategy addresses the need to identify and provide a portfolio of science themes and questions that guide the implementation of EO activities over a range of timescales, some delivering impact and benefits in the short term, and some guiding EO Programme activities over the longer term.

VISION

The EO strategic vision focuses on the steps ESA can take to address the environment, the climate crisis, and societal and economic impacts. Scientific knowledge and understanding gained from new satellite technologies and growing volumes of data provide the basis for decision-making and action, and for preparing a better tomorrow.

Vision Statement

To craft world-class Earth observation capabilities and information products for informed decisions and actions that best respond to today's challenges of understanding and sustainably managing our Earth environment.

PROLOGUE

Scientific advances in the Earth system and climate research based on EO satellite technology have exponentially increased in the last years. This is thanks to the wide variety of novel high-quality EO missions and datasets, as well as to the continuous provision of long-term data records providing fundamental evidence of climate change and its impacts worldwide.

Despite this progress, many observation and knowledge gaps remain, and the imprint of climate change and anthropogenic effects are increasing, affecting the environment at human-life scale. The following points highlight the need for urgent scientific action:

- The consequences of climate change are no longer a future threat, but a present-day reality in which the everyday effects of global warming and human pressures on the environment are more evident, frequent and intense across the globe.
- The rate of change, driven by climate change and human pressure, is accelerating taking the Earth system into new regimes and patterns within global water, carbon and energy cycles. This shift is leading to more frequent and intense regional and local extreme events, and abrupt irreversible changes can no longer be ruled out. This poses new challenges for the scientific community.
- There is a vital need to enhance our capacity to observe and characterise these new regimes in a holistic manner, advancing the fundamental scientific understanding of the underlying processes, their drivers and impacts on the Earth system, society and ecosystems, and enhancing our predictive capacity to define effective responses and adaptation measures.
- Human activity needs to be better understood as an integral component of the Earth system through the capacity to observe, characterise, understand, predict and manage the impacts of human interventions from local to global scales. This poses major challenges for our observing system and modelling capacities, which need to address unprecedented scales in both space and time.
- Feedbacks and interactions between natural ecosystems and socioeconomics can no longer be ignored. Addressing these complexities requires dedicated observing capabilities and renewed interdisciplinary scientific efforts to advance how we assess and predict the evolution of ecosystems.

As a response to these needs, the EO Science Strategy outlines ESA's science vision, presenting priorities and accompanying approaches that reflect and directly respond to scientific and societal challenges. It identifies the areas of science that ESA needs to respond to along the full value chain: from innovative missions through excellent science to societal benefits and applications. The strategy supports a range of programmatic actions including blue-sky or discovery-driven science, maturation of new mission ideas, science activities supporting mission development, research and development of novel techniques to extract information from existing data, and fostering international collaboration, among others.

A science-driven approach lies at the heart of the ESA's Earth Observation Programme as it provides the basis to increase the collective understanding our evolving planet and the development of actionable information in tackling serious global environmental issues and the resulting challenges.

The Science Strategy builds on five interconnected pillars:

- Advance blue-sky and curiosity-driven research to improve our capacity to deliver high-quality observations of our planet and changes, providing a synoptic view of its complex processes
- Address the critical scientific challenges and knowledge gaps that limit our understanding of the Earth system and its interactions and feedbacks
- Develop community capability to simulate and predict the dynamic evolution of Earth and climate system at scales in space and time compatible with societal needs

- Timely and effective transfer of scientific knowledge, data and capacity into societal benefits, informed decision-making, contributions to national and international policies and, more generally, supporting actions and green solutions that enable sustainable development for our society and economies
- Ensure effective end-to-end approach to science by ensuring a continuous feedback loop between the latest scientific advances and definition of the next generation of observing systems.

At the heart of the EO Science Strategy are overarching science themes and guiding questions that encapsulate pressing Earth system science issues and critical knowledge gaps in which satellite EO technology would provide a unique contribution, either leveraging existing or near-future EO data sources or by developing new capabilities.

The EO Science Strategy also responds to the need to illustrate where the benefits from investment in EO science can be translated into societal and policy benefits. These benefits come through a range of means, including the increasing ability to manage and protect our environment, anticipate and respond to extreme weather events and natural or human-induced disasters and through a better understanding of the dominant multidisciplinary interactive processes within the Earth system. It also comes through spin-off benefits where science-grade qualified data can be employed in operational environmental monitoring to support policy implementation and the sustainable management of Earth resources. The strategy responds by explicitly linking the overarching science themes and questions to societal benefits and policy needs, and by documenting the nature of these links.

The Earth system is complex and interconnected. Despite our ever-advancing scientific knowledge, there are still significant gaps in our understanding of this intricate system, and addressing these gaps is critical to respond to the challenges of the changing Earth and climate, and to chart courses of action. **The EO Science Strategy – and the underpinning portfolio of overarching science themes and questions – respond to these knowledge gaps over a range of timescales.** These include delivering new knowledge and reducing critical knowledge gaps in the short term (typically from 2026–2031) by leveraging data and new information provided by existing missions and by satellite missions launched during this time frame. Addressing these gaps will also require a longer-term (towards 2040) investment in new, exciting, and ambitious EO missions. These missions will allow us to explore, discover and develop new insights into our planet and provide venues to develop fit-for-purpose environmental and climate information from space, which is currently unavailable, but of absolute importance to advance our understanding. By contrast, commercial space associated with fast development cycles may offer a complementary and economically interesting path for rapidly developing additional EO capacity that addresses the science priorities and knowledge gaps within domains in which the sensing technology and the application context are already mature.

The ESA EO Science Strategy provides a longer-term vision extending to 2040, in line with the overarching ESA Strategy 2040. The strategy also serves to define ESA activities in a shorter time frame, responding to the accelerating pace of science, discovery and applications and the pressing need to develop capabilities that lead to actionable information for a sustainable environment. The priorities and strategies are intended to focus attention on those areas where ESA's EO Programme can have the greatest impact.

The EO Science Strategy is based on **four areas of action**:

- **Frontier Science and Discovery: a strong foundation**
- **From Science to Benefits: meeting society's needs**
- **Reducing Critical Knowledge Gaps: taking expedient action**
- **Filling Critical Observation Gaps: preparing for tomorrow starts today**

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OBJECTIVE OF THE EO SCIENCE STRATEGY

The ESA EO Science Strategy outlines a renewed vision and identifies a set of key scientific themes and priorities to address the challenges of our rapidly changing world. The strategy aims to promote scientific excellence whilst closing critical knowledge gaps, enabling actions with societal benefits across different timescales covering the short, medium and long term. The Science Strategy is applicable to all ESA EO Programme activities and provides a framework to connect scientific research and development, innovative new EO mission ideas and technologies, and the mission data exploitation. This approach is designed to develop EO capabilities with which to advance Earth system science and deliver tangible societal benefits. The strategy will be used to guide implementation actions within ESA's EO Programmes.

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First-class science is absolutely essential for the promotion of European interests and leadership, as it imparts a strong strategic drive to its technological and industrial system.

'Uplifting ESA Science Funding'
European Space Sciences Committee
Seville, 6 November 2023

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STRATEGIC SCIENCE PRIORITIES

Overarching Science Themes

From the inception of ESA's Living Planet Programme, the Earth science community has progressively developed the concept of the regulation of the Earth system by an integrated network of interconnected processes, fluxes, and exchanges. However, partitioning the system into 'spheres' (atmosphere, biosphere, cryosphere, geosphere, and hydrosphere) or compartments, as in previous EO strategies, is now recognised to be artificial and does not fully reflect the complex interactions between Earth system components. It risks creating boundaries that do not exist in the real world and overlooks important feedback loops, and creates disciplinary silos. The primary goal in refocusing the new Science Strategy is, therefore, to stimulate a more holistic, integrated approach to science, development of knowledge, understanding, and monitoring of the interconnected Earth system. Secondary goals are to ensure that the strategy is inclusive of the entire European EO science community, enables discovery science, and fosters the development of novel technological capabilities to unlock new scientific research and understanding.

The six overarching science themes identified by the Advisory Committee on Earth Observation as overarching scientific themes (STs) designed to engage the broader Earth science community and align with the priorities of other national and major international science strategies are:

ST-I	ST-II	ST-III	ST-IV	ST-V	ST-VI
The water cycle	The carbon cycle and chemistry	Energy fluxes	Ecosystem health	Extremes and hazards	Interfaces & coupling in the Earth system

Table 1 Overarching science themes that guide scientific priorities within EO Programmes. A detailed description of each theme can be found in Appendix 1.

Due to the integrated nature of the Earth system, these overarching science themes are interconnected and hence overlap (Figure 1). Together, they cover the most important aspects of contemporary integrated Earth system science, which can only be addressed with the support of EO techniques.

Beyond these science themes, the history of science provides ample evidence that science breakthroughs often occur through discoveries that are only made possible through blue-sky research and/or new technological developments. Hence, forthcoming implementation of this strategy strives for a balance between today's research priorities and blue-sky research with compelling justification, maintaining the prospect of a future breakthrough in understanding the Earth system.

Formulating the Science Strategy based on these overarching themes is considered a natural evolution of previous approaches, with the difference that it emphasises the integrated nature of Earth system science even more strongly than in its previous formulations. Notably, these overarching themes are also traceable to strategic science priorities identified in independent strategies including the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) Strategic Plan 2019–2028, the current WCRP lighthouse activities (formulated in 2022), and the NASA Decadal Survey 2018, along with the extensive ESA Science Strategy foundation study and user consultation workshop feedback, which all served as inputs to this strategy.

Figure 1 The interconnected nature of the Earth system and links to the six overarching scientific themes

EO allows to observe and monitor the Earth system and its changes at a wide range of spatial and temporal scales, relevant for observing natural or human-induced changes, and reducing knowledge gaps, from Earth's core to the ionosphere. Space-based observations are the only way to obtain globally consistent observations of changes across the planet. For some overarching themes, the use of novel satellite sensors and/or multi-constellation satellite data have already yielded detailed an understanding of some changes and key Earth system processes. However, gaps remain in terms of sufficient resolution in time and space to further resolve and advance the understanding of processes with a reliable accuracy.

The combination of multi-sensor satellite, airborne and in-situ observations, combined with enhanced modelling, are an important element in the development of capabilities for all overarching themes such as the water and carbon cycles, and ecosystem health. The development of higher resolution sensors, across the complete electromagnetic spectrum from the lowest radar and radiometer frequencies through optical and ultraviolet wavelengths, combined with other geophysical EO data such as gravity and magnetic field observations, provide important constraints on global change and episodic events, from the core to the outer atmosphere.

The role of multi-sensor data in leveraging future satellite constellations and novel sensor technologies are key research avenues for enhancing EO capabilities to understand the Earth system. In addition, they support the development of efficient adaptation and impacts mitigation strategies regarding extreme events such as coastal flooding, extreme precipitations events, tsunamis, landslides, earthquakes and volcanic eruptions. Predicting, and assessing the impact of hazardous events and cascading hazards (affecting both human and ecosystem health), and the improvement of preparedness and mitigation of such events, remains a key challenge in EO, and for the downstream information chains that will trigger protective actions.

Guiding Science Questions

As part of a broad horizon scan, an ESA EO Science Strategy Foundation Study, along with user consultations, allowed a set of cross-cutting scientific questions to be established and consolidated. These questions underly and provide the foundation for addressing the six overarching science themes.

Initially, fifty-seven sequential Candidate Science Questions (CSQs) were identified and documented through the study and served as the written basis for consultations with the user community. These CSQs were reviewed and discussed with ACEO at two user consultation workshops, one in 2023 and one in 2024. Additional feedback was collected from the user community via online questionnaires after each workshop. Based on the extensive feedback, 23 non-exclusive 'guiding' Scientific Questions (SQs) were shortlisted, updated and refined while retaining the original numbering. These provide a community-vetted focus for scientific activities within ESA's EO Programmes (see Table 2).

The resulting SQs identify a non-exclusive series of pressing Earth system science issues that could be addressed by using EO (in combination with other datasets), either by employing existing capabilities and soon to be launched missions, or future missions with capabilities yet to be developed. Based on the priority placed upon filling observation or knowledge gaps, the development of new technology, or the timescale of scientific returns, the span of SQs gives the potential for different impacts in terms of short-term scientific progress, policy or socio-economically relevant benefits, or longer-term fundamental, high-impact scientific advances.

Figure 2 Example of Science Question 44 (SQ44) 'Water Cycle' traced to geophysical observation needs on the far right, and to benefit areas on the left. On the right, more critical observations are identified by thicker lines, and sensor availability is indicated by traffic light colours in relation to the number of operational or approved satellites listed in the identified databases^{2,3} (with gaps in red). On the left, thicker lines indicate the degree of relevance to treaties and policies (in yellow), and other societal benefit categories (in blue).

² CEOS Database: <https://database.eohandbook.com/database/instrumenttable.aspx>

³ WMO OSCAR Database: WMO OSCAR | Observing Systems Capability Analysis and Review Tool - [Home](#)

Each SQ is accompanied by documentation containing the following elements:

- A narrative detailing the science need and rationale
- Knowledge Advancement Objectives (KAOs): these are specific numbered objectives (e.g. 44-A, 44-B, 44-C, 44-D in [Figure 2](#)) by which progress towards resolving the scientific question can be measured
- Geophysical Observables: the primary geophysical information needed to advance the science question. These are divided into priority observations and supporting observables, and where possible linked to CEOS /OSCAR database reference IDs;
- Measurement Specifications: the observation requirements for datasets providing the geophysical observables
- Other Datasets, Methods, Tools, and Models: beyond spaceborne observations, other items may be needed to address the science question. These could include non-EO datasets, new retrieval algorithms, new data-model assimilation techniques, calibration/validation facilities etc.

ST-I Water Cycle	ST-II Carbon Cycle and Chemistry	ST-III Energy Fluxes	ST-IV Ecosystem Health	ST-V Extremes and Hazards	ST-VI Interfaces and Coupling
SQ05 Coastal sea level	SQ01 Global carbon cycle	SQ05 Drivers of coastal sea level changes	SQ02 Land biosphere responses	SQ36 Seismic deformation processes	SQ07 Coastal process mediation of exchanges
SQ07 Coastal process mediation of exchanges	SQ03 Ocean carbon cycle	SQ20 Drivers of ice mass balance	SQ03 Ocean carbon cycle	SQ38 Earth's crust dynamics	SQ24 Polar and high-mountain climate relationship
SQ20 Ice mass balance	SQ08 Coastal carbon cycle	SQ21 Drivers of sea-ice state and variability	SQ08 Coastal carbon cycle	SQ44 Water cycle	SQ25 Polar Ecosystem Impacts
SQ21 Drivers of sea-ice state and variability	SQ43 Coupled energy, water and carbon cycles	SQ24 Polar and high-mountain climate relationship	SQ25 Polar Ecosystem Impacts	SQ51 Coupled litho-, atmo-, iono- and mesosphere	SQ33 Solid Earth deformation
SQ25 Polar Ecosystem Impacts	SQ52 Volcanic processes and their impact	SQ35 Erosional processes of drainage basins	SQ55 State of land ecosystems	SQ52 Volcanic processes and their impact	SQ35 Erosional processes of drainage basins
SQ33 Solid Earth deformation		SQ43 Coupled energy, water and carbon cycles	SQ56 Ecosystems transitions	SQ56 Ecosystems transition	SQ36 Seismic deformation processes
SQ43 Coupled cycles		SQ45 Climate sensitivity			SQ38 Earth's crust dynamics
SQ44 Water cycle		SQ46 Earth energy imbalance			SQ43 Coupled energy, water and carbon cycles
SQ45 Climate sensitivity		SQ48 Planetary heat exchange			SQ45 Climate sensitivity
		SQ51 Coupled litho-, atmo-, iono- and mesosphere			SQ51 Coupled litho-, atmo-, iono- and mesosphere
		SQ52 Volcanic processes and their impact			

Table 2 Overarching science themes and SQs associated with each theme guiding the implementation of activities. Appendices 1 and 2 provide a more detailed description of each theme and SQ, with the associated policy relevance and benefit areas identified in Appendices 3 and 4.

From Science to Policy and Societal Benefits

Scientific excellence and a science-focused response to the thematic priorities and scientific questions remains the main priority. The Science Strategy and SQs also address the need to be able to explain the benefits that would result from scientific research and applications development. [Figure 3](#) illustrates how each of the SQs are traced in terms of their direct relevance to societal benefits and policy domains (see Appendices 2, 3 and 4).

Figure 3 Traceability between the Science Questions (SQs) in the centre and International Agreements/Treaties on the left, and socio-economically relevant application domains on the right. See also Appendix 4 for the Policy and benefits categories and Appendix 5 for the International Agreements/Treaties and areas impacted by EO Science.

Each of the SQs summarised in [Table 2](#) are outlined in greater detail in Appendices 2 and 3, and identified by a brief descriptive text, and explicitly linked to International Treaties, Agreements and Conventions as well as National policy. In addition, benefit categories are identified in Appendix 4.

STRATEGY TIMESCALES & TIMEFRAME

The 2021 Independent Science Review of ESA's EO Programme recommended that the time horizon for the Science Strategy should be revisited and shortened, with a suggested review and revision every six years by comparison to previous decadal updates. This timescale acknowledges the accelerating pace of scientific discovery and applications development, and evolving policy landscape, and emphasises the need for more frequent reflection on scientific progress.

The Science Strategy timescale and timeframe have important implications for EO Programme implementation, and for the rates of progress of different programme elements. Exploitation of ongoing missions and available data using new methods, or novel approaches, can be used for frontier science addressing the science questions, enabling new discoveries and progress on the shortest timescale within one or two three-year programme cycles. Similarly, smaller and more expeditious missions (such as Scouts) can be implemented within a shorter timeframe to deliver new observations and scientific progress. By contrast, the development lifecycle of ambitious flagship research missions providing fundamental new types of observations may take a decade between idea and launch, only yielding scientific results after 10–15 years. Consequently, technology development for more complex future missions must be guided by scientific priorities and an architectural vision with a minimum of decadal foresight so that addressing some of the most challenging science questions, or persistent monitoring needs are feasible. Hence, the new portfolio of science questions supports activities that contribute over a range of timescales, some delivering impact and benefits in the short term, and others supporting long-term strategic goals.

The anchoring of new science-driven missions to the Earth science thematic priorities and SQs remains a key focus of the Science Strategy. Previously, the Earth Observation Envelope Programme delivered significant success, scientific progress and impact by linking the strategy to calls for mission ideas and selection of research missions. This new Science Strategy is also expected to support a range of other actions including R&D on new techniques to extract information from existing data, early-phase mission concept science, and international collaboration, amongst others. The SQs therefore include objectives that require a range of different programmatic actions to enable scientific progress, including new mission concepts, specific R&D to enable maturation of the science and technology, research on algorithms, retrievals and data assimilation.

In recognition of these considerations, the present Science Strategy reflects a short-term element spanning two three-year Programme segments, and a time horizon extending to 2040, corresponding to the ESA Strategy 2040.

STRATEGIC AREAS OF ACTION

A1 Frontier Science and Discovery: a strong foundation

Frontier science refers to the pursuit of discoveries and ideas that have not yet been supported by scientific evidence with new observations, methods or models. Stimulating excellence in novel, discovery or transformational science remains a core strategic objective for ESA, serving as the foundation for all areas of action. Frontier science and discovery plays a critical role in developing scientific knowledge about the Earth system and in addressing the overarching science themes and interconnections highlighted in [Figure 1](#). Additionally, frontier science remains fundamental to shaping and inspiring discoveries, catalysing technological advancements, developing workforce talents, industrial competencies and competitiveness, and infrastructure assets across EO Programmes. As such, it remains a high priority in science-driven EO activities.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 1

To pursue excellent, innovative, inspirational and impactful frontier science as a primary driver of innovation in EO Programmes and activities.

Frontier science is best addressed by harnessing scientific knowledge, technical resources, and know-how at a European level through ESA and, hence, remains a pillar of the new EO Science Strategy. Developing scientific knowledge and interpreting geophysical parameters through space-based observations requires upstream scientific work in activities such as, but not exclusively, understanding the physical principle of measurement, spectroscopy and radiative transfer, instrument development, calibration/validation, data analysis and algorithm development.

In addition, only by combining the space-based observations with complementary ground-based and airborne observations (dedicated campaigns or long-term measurement networks) and numerical models (including artificial intelligence, machine learning and digital twins) will it be feasible to address and fulfil the scientific questions and thematic priorities of the strategy. Notably, numerical modelling is an indispensable complement to observations, since many fundamental properties of the Earth system cannot be measured directly, but can only be determined within a physically consistent framework like Earth system models or digital twins.

Finally, ever increasing data volumes at increasing spatial or spectral resolutions require concurrent innovation in data processing methods, including the provision of uncertainty estimates. While higher spatial and temporal sampling will bring improvements in process understanding, new observational concepts and technologies are, and remain essential, to meeting the science priorities outlined in this document and to address knowledge and observation gaps.

The overarching scientific themes and SQs underpinning the new Science Strategy provide both the justification and the means to guide, prioritise and balance frontier science activities across ESA's future EO Programmes. By defining and documenting pressing Earth system science issues, identifying related geophysical information required supporting tools and models to be identified. The SQs provide a unique framework to guide the development of ambitious new satellite missions and to support highly innovative science with current and near-future EO missions.

Meanwhile, it is recognised that whilst this area of action fosters new discoveries, the process of defining how to measure or address a science question may lead to new scientific questions and/or observation gaps that can only be unravelled in the future.

Figure 4 Indication of the relevance of the SQs to understanding global climate tipping points [Global tipping points report, 2023]. The size of each circle represents the relevance to each tipping point, and the colour indicates the strength of evidence for the tipping point dynamics.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 2

To develop Earth science understanding within each of the six overarching themes by stimulating research addressing the guiding SQs.

Benefits of a frontier science-driven EO Programme include:

- Enhanced understanding of the Earth and its environment:** The scientific method combined with ambitious transformational science provides a tool for advancing our understanding of the Earth system and anthropogenically-induced interactions and changes. This knowledge is vital for making informed decisions, developing sustainable policies, and mitigating the challenges posed by environmental changes.
- Economic Growth, Innovation and Prosperity:** The advancements in technology, industry, and organisation enabled by frontier science lead to a wealth of tangible benefits. Commercial applications, job creation, overall prosperity and valuable technical, programmatic and commercial capabilities are direct outcomes of scientific innovation, fostering economic growth, societal well-being, and enhanced resilience to future global developments.
- Security:** Scientific insights gained from research underpin essential security capabilities. By bolstering Earth science, we enhance our ability to develop advanced technologies, skills and capabilities that safeguard European citizens and European geopolitical interests.

- **Risk Mitigation and Preparedness:** Many challenges and threats, such as natural disasters and climatic and environmental change, can be better anticipated, understood, and fed into concrete actions when building on the outcomes of frontier science.
- **Prestige:** New scientific discoveries, made possible through discovery EO, showcase Europe's capabilities, fostering a sense of collective pride that captivates the public imagination. These achievements also generate credibility and respect from global partners and competitors.
- **Inspiration and Education:** EO science has the unique power to inspire and engage people across all age groups and backgrounds. It enables and supports informing the public, and the building of capacity and human capital to address the future environmental challenges.

A2 From Science to Benefits: meeting society's needs

There is an ever-growing need to ensure investments in EO science benefits society or potential economic growth. Benefits are realised through the increasing capability to manage and protect our environment from a better understanding of the dominant multidisciplinary interactive processes within the Earth system, and through the spin-off benefits where data designed for science can be employed in operational environmental monitoring and evidence-based policy implementation, or be incorporated in local resource management. Each SQ is traced to potential impact in the sectors of energy, environment, food security, transport and infrastructure, civil protection, and public health (Appendix 3).

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 3

To develop scientific knowledge and capacity to deliver high-quality validated, trusted, actionable information products relevant to national, international and global policy frameworks.

A substantial number of the SQs link clearly to policy and societal benefits, which can be delivered by improving our understanding and associated green solutions development. In assessing links to policy benefits, the new Science Strategy considers four different aspects:

- **Inform:** EO science informs policy debates through the provision of knowledge, understanding and evidence. Examples include the provision of climate records and enhanced Earth system models which quantify and explain the 'how and why' our climate and environment are changing.
- **Assist:** EO science assists and supports society in addressing current and future challenges in areas such as responding to environmental issues and reducing the loss of life. Example benefits include improved weather forecasting, air quality warning, natural resources management, and responding to geohazards including warning systems and emergency response.
- **Comply:** EO science provides the basis for the future definition and enforcement of policy outcomes and legislation. Examples of this benefit include Measurement, Reporting and Verification systems used for carbon accounting, Montreal Treaty support, and policing marine protected areas.
- **Evaluate:** EO science supports assessment of the outcomes of policy decisions. An example of this benefit is the unique role of EO in monitoring the trends in greenhouse gas emissions worldwide. There is also a fast-growing need to be able to quantify the efficacy of climate adaptation measures on all scales.

These four criteria quantify the relevance to the policy domain for the themes and SQs tabled in the Strategy. A question is relevant if it provides knowledge, data, or tools to 'inform' policy and policy options, 'assist' policy delivery, ensure 'compliance' with regulations and 'evaluation' of the impact and efficacy of any enacted policy response. Relevance is assessed with respect to the main international treaties and agreements (e.g. Paris Agreement, Convention on Biodiversity, UN Sustainable Development Goals, Sendai Framework on Disaster Risk Reduction, and the EU Green Deal), or to national policy domains (energy, environment, transport and infrastructure, civil protection and humanitarian assistance, and public health).

The strength and uniqueness of the link between each SQ and the policy area is of great importance in connecting science to policy and defining priority strategic goals, alongside its relevance. In preparing the Strategy, a full assessment was carried out which is summarised in the Appendix. The strength of the contribution to each policy domain is summarised in the form of Policy-Science Question scores, and is illustrated in the form of a heat map (Figure 5). The heat map identifies low relevance scores (white) for SQs where the contribution to policy is lacking or limited, and extends to high scores (dark brown) for SQs where there is a unique, strong connection between the SQ and the international policy. For example, SQ 01 (What anthropogenic and natural processes are driving the global carbon cycle?) is in orange as the knowledge developed through science investigations directly informs Article 4 and 5 of the Paris Agreement, as well as supports the Enhanced Transparency Framework and Global Stocktake.

Figure 5 Indicative relevance of each SQ to major international policies and agreements. Scores are calculated for the relationship between each SQ and policy areas to provide a measure of the connections based on a methodology developed by the EO Science Strategy Foundation Study.

The relevance of the priority SQs to policies/societal benefits provides a sound and transparent basis to guide and prioritise future ESA EO science activities. An important subset of the priority SQs is characterised by strong to very strong contributions to national and international policies. Addressing these questions within future ESA EO Programmes will therefore greatly enhance strategic areas of action. In addition to relevance, the need to deliver actionable information is of great importance in connecting science to policy and defining priority strategic goals. In doing so, there is a need to distinguish between real end-user demand and assumed end-user demand. Bridging this gap requires scientists to engage with policymakers to jointly shape realistic demands and to ensure that research outcomes provide a solid basis for explicit decisions. These 'demand-shaping' activities should ideally occur before research and projects are designed to help researchers focus their efforts effectively.

Addressing SQs and advancing our understanding of the Earth system will benefit interdisciplinary data science. It will enable and provide an expanding basis for connecting scientists from different sectors, EO specialists, climate scientists, ecosystem scientists, social and economic scientists to jointly undertake far-reaching interdisciplinary research and to provide the quantitative basis for a scientific response to the urgent societal needs underpinning the European and global environmental and development agendas.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 4

To advance interdisciplinary science, fostering the integration of socio-economic data and EO in interdisciplinary research.

A3 Reducing Critical Knowledge Gaps: taking expedient action

The increasing number of scientific, operational and commercial satellites that will be launched in the coming years by Europe and worldwide offers an unprecedented opportunity to radically improve our capacity to holistically observe and understand the Earth system, opening the door to novel discoveries and scientific breakthroughs with significant impacts in society. This will require the timely and effective pursuit of multimission synergic opportunities offered by the wide variety of sensors and ensuring these developments and products are qualified by sound characterisation of error and uncertainties. In addition, Earth action and progress towards a green and resilient future relies strongly on scientific understanding and innovation coupled with Earth system modelling to most effectively leverage the full benefits of satellite data.

Figure 6 Timeline of ESA research and operational missions during the Science Strategy timeframe. Missions to be launched or operational during the coming years (2026–2031) and in the longer term (up to 2040) are identified. Note: this data is extracted from the CEOS database and all dates for launch/end-of-life dates are subject to change.

Building on this expanding spaceborne infrastructure and the information provided by existing and planned missions (Figure 6), SQs for which demonstrable progress can be realised by 2031 will be addressed through ESA's EO Programmes. Benefits in addressing the Earth system knowledge gaps expressed by the SQs should include:

- Increased expertise and capacity in the European upstream and downstream sectors with respect to new instruments and their exploitation for scientific and pre-operational purposes
- Consolidated scientific basis for key algorithms, ensuring that user specified information can be generated effectively and credibly with new data becoming available
- Improved, robust and fit-for-purpose Digital Twin Earth (DTE) components that build on the increased knowledge and scientific capacity developed through ESA Programmes. DTE acts as digital replicas of Earth system components, enhancing our understand of the past, monitoring the present state of the planet, assessing its changes, and simulating its potential evolution under different (what-if) scenarios at scales compatible with decision-making
- Increased users' and stakeholders' readiness to rapidly uptake derived information products within the science and applications community.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 5

To ensure the EO user community takes full advantage of the scientific opportunities offered by the existing data (including archived and long-heritage) and new missions that will be launched in the 2026–2031 timeframe, to advance understanding of Earth system and maximise scientific return.

Addressing the big-ticket science questions will require major institutional collaborations and the coordination of science programmes across the European research landscape. With the landmark joint Earth system science initiative with the EC Research and Innovation Directorate (DG-RTD) and the cooperation agreement with the Directorate General for Climate Action (DG-CLIMA), ESA and the EC are seizing the opportunity to harness combined expertise and resources to bring about transformative change in Earth and climate science.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 6

To maximise the combined impact of the ESA, EUMETSAT, national and EU investments by reciprocal reinforcement and alignment of research priorities to foster research and innovation and the use of EO data to support the green transition and climate action.

By embracing New Space approaches, which have a shorter development lifecycle of only a few years, smaller Scout-like research missions are designed to target specific science and policy questions and address knowledge gaps on shorter timescales. Complementing ESA's larger research missions, such smaller missions are developed to contribute to Earth science and practical applications, while retaining the potential to be eventually scaled up to larger monitoring missions.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 7

To demonstrate the value of more agile small research satellites as a means of filling critical observation gaps and delivering short-term answers to critical science questions.

Figure 7 Agile development of SmallSat missions such as the HydroGNSS Scout enables new measurement capabilities to fill critical knowledge gaps.

Credit: SSTL

A4 Filling Critical Observation Gaps: preparing for tomorrow starts today

Bold, fit-for-purpose and game-changing European flagship research missions have consistently addressed observation gaps and delivered unprecedented knowledge about the Earth system.

Guided by scientific priorities, deep technology development is often required to fill crucial information gaps. This requires the study and pre-development of novel and improved spaceborne observation capabilities. Certain (especially the mission-centric) components require a longer-term vision of up to a decade or more to successfully address priority science questions.

In addition to addressing the technological needs, more complex future missions require sustained scientific efforts to define, explore and further develop the science context and prepare missions, and help secure the engagement of the user community. Such sustained efforts bring many benefits including increased scientific understanding and framing of a mission's purpose and potential, innovation in terms of new approaches to data use and uptake, exploration of the value and science impact of new measurements, improved guidance to the mission development ensuring that each mission is fit-for-purpose and provides maximum science return. The process of defining how to measure or address a quantity may also foster new scientific discoveries and potentially lead to new scientific questions.

Figure 8 Field experiments – or campaigns - are essential to sustained efforts to explore, define and develop the scientific context and to guide the development of EO missions. *Credit: CPOM-A. Hogg*

The guiding SQs with highest relevance to critical observation gaps provide the scientific justification and framework for conducting the preparation of long-term investments in EO missions. The questions serve as a compass for the development of future technologies and to expanded EO capabilities.

Furthermore, it is necessary to establish a blueprint to build and maintain the optimal European EO reference architecture. This should consider existing national space capacity and initiatives within Europe. It will identify the persistent backbone of gold-standard reference missions, particularly for securing the extension of fundamental climate data records, and for supplying sustained datasets as the basis for the operational services, upon which to deliver EO-based solutions. Equally, the reference architecture relies on a system-of-systems framework that considers all components of the observing system in relation to the synergetic potential and specific observation needs. Components can be seen as missions (e.g. operational satellites, reference missions, scientific missions, commercial missions), as data and operations management, access, ground segment, technical/industrial components, modelling and decision-support or verification and certification components.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 8

To develop and implement an architectural blueprint for a sustainable EO system-of-systems to guide long-term ESA research and technology preparation, including bold flagship mission implementation addressing strategic science priorities.

Within the long-term vision expressed by the architectural blueprint, the steps needed to prepare the future transition of observations from research to operations must be foreseen and prepared to sustain critical observations. Robust technology development is recognised on the one hand as a prerequisite to make the transition, whilst bi-directional feedback must be established between the R&D activities and operational service providers to prepare the way.

ESA holds a unique position with its overall overview of the full mission life cycle.

ESTABLISHING SCIENCE PRIORITIES: ADDRESSING THE AREAS OF ACTION

The final portfolio of 23 Guiding SQs address the six overarching science themes and provide a solid basis to guide the implementation the EO Programmes in the four respective action areas A1, A2, A3, and A4. Meanwhile, by characterising and ranking each of the SQs in terms of their potential contribution to one or another strategic area of action, this would enable, for example, to identify and distinguish SQs for which significant advances in our understanding or reduction of scientific knowledge gaps could be delivered within six years, or those SQs for which we may wish to have a more direct contribution to policies and societal benefits. Similarly, if greater strategic importance is attached to filling critical observation gaps or performing discovery science on longer timescales, then different priorities could be established.

An example of an unweighted characterisation of the SQs for all four strategy action areas is provided below. [Figure 9](#) provides an example of a basis and methodology for establishing scientific priorities and implementing programmatic activities depending on the weights assigned to one or the other strategic areas of action.

Figure 9 Example framework for assessing and characterising the SQs in terms of the four areas of action

ENABLING TOOLS FOR ACTION

Building Partnerships and Cooperation

Strategic partnerships and cooperative initiatives are widely recognised to be essential when engaging actors, both within and beyond the space sector, especially when coordinated efforts between science, business, governments, international organisations, and citizens alike are needed. This holds particularly when addressing global emergencies and the need to change behaviour to minimise the human footprint.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 9

Promote and strengthen collaboration with national agencies and programmes, international partner space agencies (e.g. EUMETSAT, NASA, JAXA) and other key space actors and spacefaring nations, expanding ESA and European capacity to address the priority science questions and actively engage in Earth science action.

Partnerships or collaborative efforts linking national missions of ESA Member States' national programmes are recognised as beneficial towards building the broader community of practice required to tackle some of the key strategic science challenges. Similarly, cross-sector partnerships with key public and private stakeholders are essential to bridge demand and offer downstream solutions that lead more effectively to adoption, ultimately enabling impactful decision-making and actions informed by EO.

Recent landmark initiatives between ESA and the European Commission, such as with DG-CLIMA, DG-RTD, DG-CNECT and DG-INTPA enhance our joint capabilities to better understand and address the impacts of climate change and to respond to the European Green Deal, even at a global scale. Strategic partnerships that ESA established with major mandated international policy makers and international financial institutions leverage financial resources and political processes to scale scientifically-proven EO solutions across countries and mainstream them into a wide range of socio-economic sectors. ESA will therefore continue to reinforce and build cooperation with key European partners such as EUMETSAT, ECMWF and the European Commission (AGRI, CLIMA, CNCT, DEFIS, INTPA, JRC, RTD, ENV), as well as with international space agency actors, UN organisations (e.g. FAO, UNEP, UNESCO, WMO) and international financial institutions (e.g. ADB, WB, IMF).

Fostering a Community Approach to Science

Adopting a community and collaborative approach to science through the ESA Science Clusters aims to jointly address the major science challenges in a coordinated manner. The goal is to bring teams and projects together with different expertise, data and resources in a synergistic manner.

The approach will be supported by broad participation and direct engagement of the scientific community in ESA activities, through dedicated mechanisms, such as the new Earth System Science Hub as a centre for scientific collaboration, networking and open cooperative research with world-class scientists in Member States and worldwide.

As part of this Strategy, ESA will foster a strong and coordinated approach to science contributing to an effective European research area through a close coordination and alignment of scientific priorities with Horizon Europe through the ESA-EC Earth System Science Initiative, and other major national science funding programmes and institutions, as well as promoting joint scientific actions with partner space agencies.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 10

Foster a community approach to science through dedicated mechanisms (e.g., ESA Science Clusters, Earth System Science Hub), promoting a continuous dialogue and wide participation of the scientific community to ESA activities at both European and international level, maximising synergies across teams and disciplines and ensuring a collective, collaborative scientific contribution to address the Strategy SQs.

Building Strong STEM Education, Training and Outreach

To prepare the next generation of ESA EO scientists and practitioners, and to engage early-career scientists in research and science activities, it is essential to strengthen education and training programmes in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) at all educational levels.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 11

Dedicate appropriate level of support to the preparation of the next generation of European EO scientists through dedicated training and education activities.

ESA should maximise the outreach and dissemination of EO science results not only towards the scientific community (e.g., by advanced open science tools), but mainly towards the general public, policy-makers, non-space experts and stakeholders, and especially towards the young generation through advanced immersive visualisation capabilities, interactive dashboards, and novel communication means.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 12

Maximise the outreach and communications of ESA EO scientific results towards the general public, policy-makers and particularly towards younger generations.

Exploring EO Science Links with Commercial Space

Commercial satellites represent a new and relatively unexplored source of data to support advances in our understanding of the Earth system. Hybrid public and commercial constellations have the potential to enhance both the temporal and spatial resolution of observations, and integrating the data from commercial and institutional missions can enable more comprehensive and integrated analysis in response to the strategic science questions. The SQs provide a useful reference to further explore the potential of commercial space missions not only by providing the scientific objectives and context, but also by specifying the geophysical information needed to address the questions. Requirements such as observation type, and the role and suitability of data products and commercial data provision in addressing the science questions, need to be quantified. In addition, the feasibility of integrating scientific data quality metrics, or 'quality stamp', in commercial solutions and data needs to be determined as a prerequisite for scientific uptake and use. This would allow the benefits to be realised of integrating available or future commercial EO data and services into the data ecosystem.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 13

To explore the complementary capabilities of commercial space as a new vehicle to accelerate and address science priorities and to serve the science community.

Harnessing Open Science through Digital Innovation

FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) foundational principles, together with open science and open innovation, provide a significant opportunity to collectively contribute and harness the power of cutting-edge digital technologies in delivering validated, trusted and actionable information. Working with diverse remote-sensing data and research data management platforms throughout the 'measure-understand-predict-decide-action cycle' is crucial to be able to effectively address the priority SQs. To this end, modern, powerful and agile open infrastructures have become essential enablers for scientific research and applications supporting a wide range of sectors.

Building such solutions with a long-term perspective, supported by capacity building and wide and open education on FAIR and open science, fosters institutional and scientific collaboration and promotes a scientific process that is both equitable and inclusive. Open as well as federated approaches to the enabling technologies and practices lead to infrastructures that are inherently more accessible, as well as resilient, sustainable and safe. However, they rely on interoperability, evolving standards and, most importantly, community participation. In fact, much of the essential underlying open-source supporting EO industry today relies on voluntary effort.

Figure 10 Application of open science principles to stimulate and accelerate scientific progress and open innovation.

The long-term sustainability of the open innovation ecosystem depends on the institutional support to grow capability, competitiveness and to educate. Supporting the evolution and growth of this ecosystem is therefore not just desirable, but a necessity. Open innovation fosters a networked approach, maximising knowledge exchange, resource optimisation, cost reduction and sustainability. It also promises to maximise stakeholder engagement when combined with user-centric approaches, accelerating value creation and improving transparency and trust. A strong engagement is necessary through up-to-date policies, enabling technology and inclusive partnerships. Such an approach will foster research data discoveries and for the resulting information to be FAIR and open to the maximum extent possible and/or as closed as necessary, while maintaining high standards of security and privacy.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 14

To foster the development of a culture and practice of openness in EO science, applications and industry, and of a sustainable open innovation ecosystem.

The multiplication of data sources from satellites, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) or High-Altitude Pseudo Satellites (HAPS), combined with Internet of Things (IoT) holds the potential to reshape EO, offering new opportunities for science and entrepreneurship. Artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning

have already demonstrated their value in maximising multidisciplinary exploitation of the growing big data resource. Strengthening and integrating evolving AI capabilities within ESA and the European data pipeline is therefore paramount to maximise the benefits of EO investments.

Figure 11 Harnessing digital innovation and the enabling tools to develop an improved scientific understanding and representation of the Earth system as input to the digital twin framework.

The combination of EO, societal data and IoT with the AI evolution and the availability of vast computational power, offered by hybrid High Performance Computing (HPC) – Quantum Computing (QC), offers immense opportunities to advance and improve Earth system modelling, revolutionising resource and hazard management and stimulate the EO downstream sector.

In terms of societal benefits, the evolution of EO cloud-based ecosystems promises more versatile capabilities that foster uptake and fuel EO-based science towards operational value-adding on-demand services. This has the potential of lowering the adoption barrier for EO-driven solutions by new users, including key decision-makers.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 15

To develop and enhance European capabilities for harnessing digital innovation, such as AI, to maximise the exploitation of EO data for scientific and socio-economic benefits.

Opportunities also exist beyond the traditional EO domains in non-EO sectors such as data science, as other mature digital technologies offer vast untapped potential. Collaboration with non-EO actors across the different impact sectors integrating non-EO data assets (such in-situ data, socio-economic and other contextual data) is therefore also essential to deliver customised solutions addressing end-user needs. Collaboration amongst scientists and between scientists and industry/institutions is what ultimately drives the 'health' of this ecosystem. ESA can play a pivotal role by driving technological innovation, facilitating networking and 'match-making', and by supporting capacity building and EO data uptake in developing countries. Data access remains a key area to enable reproducible science. Alignment and harmonisation with international partners on standards and interoperability is essential to unlock new frontiers of discovery and innovation.

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVE 16

To facilitate cross-disciplinarity, cooperation and engagement of complementary communities and their expertise into the EO scientific and innovation processes.

ASSESSING PROGRESS

ESA's EO Science Strategy outlines a set of cross-cutting priority SQs, which together with the identified strategic objectives, can be employed as a framework for prioritising EO Programme implementation.

Future programme implementation actions, such as the calls for proposed mission ideas and selection, or calls for scientific studies, can be indexed or referenced to each of the overarching science themes and guiding SQs. This allows the scientific progress and output to be tracked and assessed in relation to the degree to which the observation gaps and knowledge advancement objectives have been addressed or fulfilled, and/or in terms of the impact and short-term benefits.

Assessment of progress can be structured along the lines of the four key areas of strategic action which have been defined, and in terms of the distribution of progress and achievements of activities addressing the selected priority SQs. Metrics involving peer-reviewed publications assessment, advancement of science readiness level, uptake of and use of data, preparation of analysis-ready datasets, quantified improvements in model predictive skill, or socio-economic or policy impact (e.g., measured through uptake of ESA information products) may be defined in relation to each area of action.

On this basis, it is proposed that the ideal time horizon for periodically revisiting progress assessments corresponds to the six-year timescale required to measure substantive scientific progress. This matches with the timespan of durability of the SQs and strategic priorities and defines the interval at which the content of the Strategy should optimally be revisited, progress reviewed and strategic priorities reevaluated.

Appendix 1: Overarching Science Themes

ST-I: Water Cycle

This theme focuses on understanding the distribution, fluxes, and states of water (ice, liquid or vapour) within the Earth system. Key priorities include studying the drivers of changes in water reservoirs (e.g., oceans, mountain snow, ice cap and glacier mass, atmospheric water, and ground and land surface water storage), interactions between water in different phases and between compartments (e.g. water–carbon, water–energy, etc.), and the impact of human-driven water management on the water cycle. The theme emphasises the interconnectedness of water with other Earth system processes like the carbon and biogeochemical cycles and energy fluxes, as well as with weather-related hydrological extremes and ecosystem health.

ST-II: Carbon Cycle and Chemistry

This theme addresses the role of long-lived greenhouse gases in driving climate change, emphasising the need to reduce uncertainties in knowledge of carbon, methane, and nitrogen stocks and their flows, whether of natural or anthropogenic origin. It highlights the importance of understanding the processes that control gas exchanges between the atmosphere, oceans and land, and developing the capability to model and predict future changes in these exchange processes whether they are physical, chemical or biogeochemical. For the atmosphere it recognises the role of atmospheric chemistry, transport and chemical transport processes and their impact on climate change, air quality, and human and ecosystem health. It also emphasises the response of the ocean component of the carbon cycle to atmospheric trace gas burdens, including ocean acidification, biological carbon pump and marine biogeochemistry from the open ocean to the coast. For land, it includes the impact of agricultural practices on soil carbon storage potential, vegetation response to climatic disturbances and anthropogenic pressures.

ST-III: Energy Fluxes

Energy fluxes between and within Earth system compartments are crucial for identifying feedbacks related to climate change and for quantifying the physical state of the Earth system. These fluxes occur within the Earth system but can also originate from outside (i.e., from the Sun) or be initiated deep in Earth's interior and propagate outward into the near-Earth environment (e.g. heat flow and mantle hot spots). This theme stresses the need to quantify energy fluxes at global and regional scales, for example focusing on the Earth Energy Imbalance (EEI) caused by greenhouse gases and resulting adjustments and feedbacks. Understanding these fluxes is essential for validating climate models and predicting environmental changes, as well as understanding the impacts of energy imbalance upon the other Earth system cycles, and processes regulating the biosphere and accompanying ecosystems. Similarly, changes in heat reservoirs also may lead to stress or extreme events in the atmosphere, ocean and cryosphere, with corresponding impacts on the biosphere.

ST-IV: Ecosystem Health

Ecosystem health is a requisite for healthy and sustainable life on Earth. It is defined as the ability of ecosystems to provide services for humans sustainably while preserving their natural functions, intrinsic well-being and biodiversity. Advancing the understanding of ecosystem health includes all aspects of the complex interactions between organisms and their physical environment on land, in inland waters, coastal regions and oceans, whether natural or managed. Therefore, this theme is strongly linked to the other overarching topics of the water cycle, carbon cycle and chemistry, energy fluxes and extremes. It highlights the need to understand ecosystem dynamics, resilience, and the impact of natural and anthropogenic stressors (such as nutrient deficiency, eutrophication, acidification, disease, overfishing, deforestation and pollution). Also, it emphasises the importance of reliable and systematic observations to assess ecosystem structure, function, and the effects of climate change and human activities on ecosystem health and habitat.

ST-V: Extremes and Hazards

This theme focuses on extreme weather and climate events, as well as geophysical hazards such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, landslides and tsunamis. Ocean extremes threaten living organisms, marine and coastal ecosystems and communities. On land, extreme weather, heatwaves, fires, droughts and floods impact ecosystems, agricultural yields, infrastructure and cities. Beyond extremes fuelled by climate change, dynamic processes are also key actors in the Earth system, and can evolve non-linearly, leading to hazardous events. This emphasises the need to monitor and understand the underlying processes and feedbacks, to better predict events, to build resilience and to mitigate risks and protect communities. The interconnectedness of these extremes with other Earth system processes, such as energy fluxes and water cycles, is also highlighted. Coupling between the Earth's surface and its near-space environment during extreme tectonic or volcanic events is similarly emphasised. This results in climate change feedbacks due to vertical propagation of waves and gaseous or particulate emissions that can change the albedo of the surface, or change the composition and energy balance of the atmosphere.

ST-VI: Interfaces and Coupling

The study of interfaces between different Earth system components (e.g., land–ocean, atmosphere–cryosphere, atmosphere–ocean, atmosphere–biosphere, lithosphere–cryosphere etc.) is crucial for understanding the exchange of water, gas, heat and momentum that drive weather and climate dynamics, and how these evolve in time and space. This theme stresses the challenges of modelling these couplings and the need for precise observations at the requisite scales to understand Earth's response to natural and anthropogenic forces. Interfaces and exchanges occur at boundaries that are key for human activities and wellbeing. The coastal zone, for instance, is an interface that plays a critical role for human development and the exchange of nutrients, sediment, water and energy between the land, atmosphere and ocean. Representation of the processes occurring at such interfaces, and the couplings across them together with the feedbacks, is fundamental for understanding our planet and its evolution owing to anthropogenic and natural forcings. Observations at various scales of the coupling across interfaces are therefore required to provide unique insights such as the response of the solid Earth to changes in surface loading, how hurricane intensity and frequency is influenced by air–ocean fluxes or how ocean productivity depends on heat, carbon and nutrient exchange with land and atmosphere.

Appendix 2: The Overarching Science Themes, Guiding Science Questions and their Relevance to International Treaties, Agreements and Conventions

Theme(s)	(ID)	Science Question	Paris Agreement	Convention on Biodiversity	Sustainable Development Goals	Sendai Framework	EU Green Deal
Carbon Cycle and Chemistry	SQ1	What anthropogenic and natural processes are driving the global carbon cycle?	Major contribution to informing Article 4 Mitigation and evaluating policy responses; Major contribution to Article 5 on maintaining sinks and reservoirs, both terrestrial and ocean; Other contribution to Enhanced Transparency Framework and Global Stocktake	Informs Articles 6/7/8/9 pm measures, monitoring, in-situ conservation and ex-situ conservation	Major contribution to SDG 13 Climate Action	N/A	Contributes to policy goals Net Zero by 2050 and Clean, Affordable Energy
Ecosystem Health	SQ2	How has the land biosphere responded to human activity and climate change?	Major contribution to informing Article 4 policy on climate state; Major contribution to Article 5 on maintaining land/biosphere sinks and reservoirs; Potential to assist adaptation policy and Global Stocktake	Major contribution to Article 9 Ex-situ conservation; Inform/ evaluate contribution to Articles 6, 7, 8, 11 and 13; Needed to assess impact of financing measures	Major contribution to SDG15 Life on Land; Informs policy goal on SDG13 Climate action	N/A	Contributes to Net Zero by 2050; Strong contribution to Ecosystems and Biodiversity policy
Carbon Cycle and Chemistry Ecosystem Health	SQ3	How has the ocean carbon cycle responded to anthropogenic CO2 and climate change?	Relevance to Article 4 Mitigation, reporting on climate state; Informs Article 5 on ocean sink status and potential to assist policy delivery	Some relevance to Article 6 on measures for conservation; Some relevance to Article 7 on identification and monitoring;	Relevance to SDG13 Climate action and SDG14 Life below water	N/A	Some relevance to Net Zero by 2050
Water Cycle Energy Fluxes	SQ5	What processes drive changes sea level in the coastal ocean?	Some relevance to Article 4 on climate state and Article 5 ocean sinks; Strong contribution to Article 7 on adaptation and Article 8 Minimise loss and damage	Some relevance to Article 6/7/13 incl. impacts on conservation measures for coastal habitats	Strong relevance to SDG11 Sustainable cities and costal population/ development; Relevance to SDG13/14/15 pertaining to climate action, life below water and life on land	Informing Priorities 1/2/3/4 for coastal risk assessment and adaptation policies; Informs financing of prevention measures	Informs urgency of Net Zero by 2050
Water Cycle Interfaces and Coupling	SQ7	How do physical, biological and biogeochemical processes mediate exchanges between land, atmosphere and the ocean in the coastal region?	Relevance to Articles 4/5/7/8	N/A	Some relevance to SDG14 Life below Water	N/A	N/A
Carbon Cycle and Chemistry	SQ8	How are coastal areas contributing to the global carbon cycle, and how are they responding to climate change and human pressures?	Medium relevance to Article 4 mitigation; Some contribution to Article 5 maintaining ocean sink	Article 7/13 some relevance to Identification/ Monitoring and Public education	Some relevance to SDG14 Life below water	N/A	Indirect relevance to Net Zero policy

Appendix 2: The Overarching Science Themes, Guiding Science Questions and their Relevance to International Treaties, Agreements and Conventions

Theme(s)	(ID)	Science Question	Paris Agreement	Convention on Biodiversity	Sustainable Development Goals	Sendai Framework	EU Green Deal
Water Cycle Carbon Cycle and Chemistry	SQ20	What are the drivers of ice-sheet and glacier mass balance and snow cover change and what are the impacts of such changes in the Earth system?	Strong contribution to informing Article 4 Mitigation; Strong relevance to Article 7/8 on adaptation and minimising loss and damage; Strong public relevance	Article 7 Identification and monitoring of Arctic habitat	Relevance to SDG13/14/15 Climate action and life on land/ below water	Indirect relevance to understanding disaster risk via to sea level	Informs Net Zero policy
Energy Fluxes	SQ21	What are the physical processes that drive the sea ice state and its variability?	Informs Article 4 Mitigation on climate state and sensitivity; Indirect contribution to Article 5/& on adaptation, loss and damage	N/A	N/A	N/A	Indirect relevance to Net Zero policy
Energy Fluxes Interfaces and Coupling	SQ24	What is the relationship between changes in polar and high mountain regions and global climate variability	Relevance to Article 4/5 on mitigation and maintaining sinks/reservoirs	N/A	Link to SDG13 Climate action	N/A	Indirect relevance to Net Zero policy
Water Cycle Ecosystem Health	SQ25	How does the cryosphere impact on Polar ecosystems, and how is the changing climate altering these feedbacks?	Informs Article 4 mitigation policy; Some relevance to Article 5 and 7	Strong relevance across all CBD Articles; Strong role for public education and awareness	Relevance to SDG15 Life on Land	N/A	Relevance to Ecosystems and biodiversity policy
Water Cycle Interfaces and Coupling	SQ33	How does the solid Earth deform under present and past ice loads and what does it tell us about its rheology?	N/A	N/A	Relevance to SDG11 Sustainable cities and SDG15 Life on Land	Strong relevance to all Sendai Priorities	N/A
Energy Fluxes Interfaces and Coupling	SQ35	Can we quantify mass movement and erosional processes of drainage basins and the resulting sediments discharge to the oceans?	N/A	N/A	Some relevance to SDG15 Life on Land	Good relevance to all Sendai Priorities	N/A
Extremes and Hazards Interfaces and Coupling	SQ36	Can we observe, model and forecast the deformation processes, emissions and surface temperature due to volcanism during all phases of the seismic cycle?	N/A	N/A	Relevance to SDG11 Sustainable Cities and SDG15 Life on Land	Strong relevance across all Sendai priorities	N/A

Appendix 2: The Overarching Science Themes, Guiding Science Questions and their Relevance to International Treaties, Agreements and Conventions

Theme(s)	(ID)	Science Question	Paris Agreement	Convention on Biodiversity	Sustainable Development Goals	Sendai Framework	EU Green Deal
Extremes and Hazards	SQ38	How do geodynamic processes in the core and mantle evolve and interact with Earth's surface and how do they influence Earth surface and internal structure?	N/A	N/A	Relevance to SDG11 Sustainable Cities and SDG15 Life on Land	Strong relevance across all Sendai priorities	N/A
Water Cycle Carbon Cycle and Chemistry Energy fluxes	SQ43	What are the main coupling determinants between Earth's energy, water and carbon cycles; and how accurately can we predict the forcings and feedbacks between the different components of the Earth System?	Very strong relevance for Article 4 Mitigation	N/A	N/A	N/A	Relevance to Net Zero by 2050
Water Cycle Extremes and Hazards	SQ44	How important are anthropogenic and climate processes in modifying the water cycle, and how accurately can we predict the changes in time and space?	Strong relevance to Article 4 Mitigation; Contributes to Article 7/8 on adaptation and minimising loss and damage	Useful input to all Article of CBD	Informs SDG6 on clean water and sanitation; Strong input to SDG11/13/15 due to impact on life and society	Very strong contribution to all Sendai priorities due to the high % of hydro-met losses	Links with Net Zero policy and Ecosystems/ Biodiversity policy
Water Cycle Energy Fluxes	SQ45	How can we reduce the uncertainties in climate sensitivity while improving estimates of the internal flow of energy within the climate system?	Very strong relevance to Article 4 on climate state and sensitivity	N/A	N/A	N/A	Indirect link to Net Zero policy
Energy Fluxes	SQ46	How does the Earth energy imbalance and Earth heat inventory change over time and why?	Very strong relevance to Article 4 on climate state and sensitivity	N/A	N/A	N/A	Indirect link to Net Zero policy
Energy Fluxes	SQ48	How can we improve the monitoring and understanding of planetary heat exchange at regional scale?	Very strong relevance to Article 4 on climate state and sensitivity	N/A	N/A	N/A	Indirect link to Net Zero policy

Appendix 2: The Overarching Science Themes, Guiding Science Questions and their Relevance to International Treaties, Agreements and Conventions

Theme(s)	(ID)	Science Question	Paris Agreement	Convention on Biodiversity	Sustainable Development Goals	Sendai Framework	EU Green Deal
Energy Fluxes Extremes and Hazards Interfaces and Coupling	SQ51	What are the mechanisms that couple the lithosphere, atmosphere, ionosphere and magnetosphere, and can they be modelled and monitored to advance understanding in the area of geohazard risk and space weather related science?	N/A	N/A	N/A	Informs all Sendai Priorities	N/A
Carbon Cycle and Chemistry Energy Fluxes Extremes and Hazards Interfaces and Coupling	SQ52	How can we improve the understanding of volcanic processes by better monitoring and modelling volcanic events and their associated impacts on the volcanic hazard forecast through combined analysis of different domain variables?	Relevance for Article 7 (7.7.c.: “Strengthening scientific knowledge on climate, including research, systematic observation of the climate system and early warning systems, in a manner that informs climate services and supports decision-making”).	N/A	Relevance to SDG10 Reduce inequalities, SDG11 Sustainable cities, SDG13 Climate action, and SDG15 Life on Land.	Relevance to Priorities 1, 2 and 4	Relevance to sustainability and security, specifically: - Clean, affordable, secure energy - ‘Farm to fork’ sustainable food system - Sustainable mobility
Ecosystem Health	SQ55	What are local patterns of ecosystem structure composition and functions worldwide?	Informs most Articles of the Paris Agreement	Strong relevance across all Articles of the CBD	Strong link to SDG14 Life on land; Relevance to SDG12 Climate action	N/A	Strong relevance to Ecosystems and Biodiversity policy
Ecosystem Health Extremes and Hazards	SQ56	Where and how are ecosystems undergoing critical transitions?	Informs most Articles of the Paris Agreement	Strong relevance across all Articles of the CBD	Strong link to SDG14 Life on land; Relevance to SDG12 Climate action	N/A	Strong relevance to Ecosystems and Biodiversity policy

Appendix 3: Science Questions & Relevance to National Policies

Science Question		Energy	Environment	Agriculture, Food security	Transport & infrastructure	Civil Protection & humanitarian aid	Public Health
SQ1	Global carbon cycle	Informs Net Zero transition and emission reduction policy	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ2	Land biosphere responses	N/A	Strong relevance to Nature and Biodiversity policy; Relevance to Soil and Land policy; Some impact on urban environment	Farm to fork emissions; Increased production	N/A	N/A	Habitat change linked with vector borne disease risk;
SQ3	Ocean carbon cycle	Informs Net Zero transition	N/A	Sustainable fisheries	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ5	Coastal sea level	Informs energy transition; Transition risk to renewable assets; Informs Energy security	Informs marine and costal environment policy; Impact on Urban environment policy (risk)	N/A	Informs risk to land transport; Informs maritime transport infrastructure and other infrastructure categories (e.g., ports)	Strong relevance to understanding disaster risk; Contributes to enhanced risk preparedness and increase risk resilience	N/A
SQ7	Coastal process mediation of exchanges	Informs and assists coastal renewable sources (tide, wind)	Informs marine and costal environment policy	Informs sustainable fisheries	N/A	Informs risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	N/A
SQ8	Coastal carbon cycle	Informs and assists coastal renewable sources (tide, wind)	Informs marine and costal environment policy	Informs food security, sustainable fisheries and increased production	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ20	Ice mass balance	Informs and assists coastal renewable sources (tide, wind)	N/A	N/A	Impacts on maritime transport; Inform risk to supporting infrastructure	Informs risk understanding and preparedness, esp. to maritime communities	N/A
SQ21	Drivers of sea-ice state and variability	Informs renewable energy transition	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ24	Polar climate relationship	Informs energy transition	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ25	Polar ecosystem impacts	Informs energy transition	Informs Nature and Biodiversity policy	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Appendix 3: Science Questions & Relevance to National Policies

Science Question		Energy	Environment	Agriculture, Food security	Transport & infrastructure	Civil Protection & humanitarian aid	Public Health
SQ33	Solid Earth deformation	Informs transition risk, risk to assets	Relevance to urban environment policy	N/A	Informs risk to land transport and supporting infrastructure	Strong contribution to risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	N/A
SQ35	Erosional processes	Informs transition risk, risk to assets	Relevance to urban environment policy; Good link to Soil and land policy	N/A	Informs risk to land transport and supporting infrastructure	Some contribution to risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	N/A
SQ36	Seismic deformation processes	Informs transition risk, risk to assets	Relevance to urban environment policy	N/A	Informs risk to land transport and supporting infrastructure	Strong contribution to risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	N/A
SQ38	Earth's crust dynamics	Informs transition risk, risk to assets	Relevance to urban environment policy	N/A	Informs risk to land transport and supporting infrastructure	Strong contribution to risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	N/A
SQ43	Coupled cycles	Net Zero transition; Informs emission reduction strategy	Relevant to Marine & coastal environment; Relevance to Water policy and Soil and land policy	Informs farm to fork emissions, food security and increased production	Informs risk to land, maritime and air transport	N/A	Improved understanding of vector borne, respiratory and temperature related health risks
SQ44	Water cycle	Informs renewable energy transition; Informs transition risk, risk to assets	Relevant to Marine & coastal environment; Strong relevance to Water policy and Soil and land policy	Strong input to food security and increased production; Support to understanding farm to fork emissions	Risk of inundation to all forms of transport and supporting infrastructure	Improved weather and flood risk models improve risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	Strong contribution to improved understanding of waterborne, health risks
SQ45	Climate sensitivity	Net Zero transition; Informs emission reduction strategy	Informs water policy	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ46	Earth energy imbalance	Net Zero transition; Informs emission reduction strategy	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SQ48	Planetary heat exchange	Net Zero transition; Informs emission reduction strategy	N/A	Informs food security and sustainable fisheries policy	N/A	N/A	Links with respiratory and temperature related health risks

Appendix 3: Science Questions & Relevance to National Policies

Science Question		Energy	Environment	Agriculture, Food security	Transport & infrastructure	Civil Protection & humanitarian aid	Public Health
SQ51	Coupled litho-, atmo-, iono- and mesosphere	N/A	N/A	N/A	Impacts on air transportation	Some contribution to risk understanding, preparedness and resilience	N/A
SQ52	Volcanic processes and their impact	Net Zero transition; Informs emission reduction strategy (improved understanding of volcanic forcing in climate models).	Relevance to Soil and Land policy; Some impact on urban environment (800 million people exposed to some degree of volcanic hazard, with implications for long term planning for infrastructure resilience).	Volcanic ash deposited on crops impacts agriculture. Global cooling by a large volcanic eruption may affect agriculture productivity.	Strong contribution to aviation hazard assessment: support to Volcanic Ash Advisory Centers (VAAC) via Volcano Observatory Notices for Aviation (VONA). Local infrastructure may be destroyed or damaged by ash deposits, lava flows, lahars and pyroclastic flows.	Strong contribution to risk understanding, preparedness and resilience (support to local volcano observatories and civil protection agencies for emergency planning and volcanic eruption forecast; provides observations to CEOS International Charter on Space and Major Disasters (https://disasterscharter.org)).	Improved understanding of health risks due to air and water pollution. Support to Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service. UN convention on long-range transboundary air pollution.
SQ55	State of land ecosystems	N/A	Strong contribution to Nature and Biodiversity policy; Contribution to soil and land policy	Informs increased production and food security policy	N/A	N/A	Range of links ecosystem function and pest and pathogen disease risk
SQ56	Ecosystems transition	N/A	Strong contribution to Nature and Biodiversity policy; Contribution to soil and land policy; Informs marine and coastal policy	Informs increased production and food security policy	N/A	N/A	Range of links ecosystem function and pest and pathogen disease risk

Appendix 4: Policy and benefits categories

Policy / benefit domain	Components	Major international treaties/ agreements	Relevant international bodies/agencies	UN SDGs	EU DGs and EAs
Energy and climate action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy policy - Climate mitigation - Climate adaptation - Climate finance 	UNFCCC Paris Agreement REDD	IPCC IEA TCFD WB/IADB/ADB/IMF	7 Affordable and clean energy 13 Climate action 15 Life on land	ENER CLIMA CINEA
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature and biodiversity - Air quality and ozone - Water quality - Forestry - Coastal & marine environment 	CBD Ramsar Convention Montreal Protocol Kigali Amendment LRTAP Convention Ambient Air Quality Directive	UNEP IPBES TNFD UN ECE	6 Clean water and sanitation 13 Climate action 14 Life below water 15 Life on land	ENV
Agriculture, fisheries and food security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food production - Food supply chain - International commodities - Fisheries 	Common Agriculture Policy	UN FAO UN WFP IFAD IMO	2 Zero hunger 13 Climate action	AGRI MARE (Fisheries)
Transport and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air/maritime/land transport - Smart cities and urban - Regional development 	SOLAS, MARPOL	IMO ICAO IBRD WB/IADB/ADB/IMF	13 Climate action 14 Life below water 11 Sustainable cities and communities	MOVE MARE (Maritime transport) REGIO
Civil protection and humanitarian aid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disaster risk reduction/resilience - Emergency response - International humanitarian response 	Sendai Framework	UN HCR UN OCHA UN DP ICRC/IFRC	15 Life on land	ECHO
Public health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health - Social wellbeing - Disease risk - Accident and emergency 		WHO UN DP	3 Good health and well being 15 Life on land	SANTE HERA

Appendix 5: International Agreements and Treaties and Policy areas impacted by addressing the Science Questions

Treaty/Agreement	Policy goals/objectives
Paris Agreement (following Heggelin et al)	Article 4 Mitigation (incl Climate state and Climate sensitivity) Article 5 Maintaining sinks and reservoirs (incl land/biosphere and ocean) Article 7 Adaptation Article 8 Minimizing loss and damage Article 12 Public engagement Article 13 Enhanced Transparency Framework Article 14 Global Stocktake
Convention on Biodiversity (CBD)	Article 6 General Measures for Conservation and Sustainable Use Article 7 Identification and Monitoring Article 8 In-situ Conservation Article 9 Ex-situ Conservation Article 11 Incentive Measures Article 13 Public Education and Awareness
UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	SDG1 No poverty SDG2 Zero hunger SDG3 Good health & wellbeing SDG4 Quality education SDG5 Gender equality SDG6 Clean water, sanitation SDG7 Affordable, clean energy SDG8 Work & economic growth SDG9 Industry, innovation SDG10 Reduced inequalities SDG11 Sustainable cities SDG13 Climate action SDG14 Life below water SDG15 Life on land
Sendai Framework on Disaster Risk Reduction	Priority 1: Understanding disaster risk Priority 2: Strengthening disaster risk governance to manage disaster risk Priority 3: Investing in disaster risk reduction for resilience Priority 4: Enhancing disaster preparedness for effective response
EU Green Deal	Net Zero by 2050 (incl Climate Law) - Clean, affordable, secure energy - Circular economy - Energy efficiency - Zero pollution - Ecosystems and biodiversity (incl EU Taxonomy) - Farm to fork sustainable food system - Sustainable mobility

